

Fuzzy Logic Based Regression Testing: A Review

Kanika Budhwar
Research scholar

Guru Jambheshwar University (GJUS&T)

Id: kanikabudhwar@gmail.com

Parul Chhabra
Research scholar

Guru Jambheshwar University (GJUS&T)

Id: parul15march@gmail.com

Abstract: In this review paper, an advanced Regression Testing model using Fuzzy Logic is discussed. Several researches and models are there related to Regression Testing in Software Testing which are discussed in this research work. But, existing regression testing models are unable to resolve several testing problems because of some limitations. As there is rapid advent of latest programming tools and logics, different type of issues are arising. Fuzzy logic is supposed to deal with different type of challenges in Regression Testing. Therefore, there is need to integrate fuzzy logic in regression testing model to resolve issues in testing of software models. The proposed fuzzy logic based model would be beneficial to resolve the issues related to software testing. It would be used to know and decide which one performs best. This work would be helpful in future for those who want to know about Regression testing and its different techniques.

Keyword: Software Testing, Regression Testing, Fuzzy Logic, Matlab

[1]INTRODUCTION

Modern software is highly modular, emerge importance and necessity of a regression testing mechanism during the development and modification of software. During the software evolution, the enhanced size of its modifications may make increment in cost of its regression integration testing. Therefore it is essential to have a mechanism to reduce the resource expenditure and testing cost. For this purpose, the test suite reduction is a considerable method for solving this issue of Software testing. These methods are also able to provide an objective, independent view related to software. The techniques related to the test suit reduction allow business to appreciate and understand risks and issues related to the implementation software projects. Along with these feature, these test techniques are also included the process of executing a software bugs free program or application. In the process of these test suit reduction, verifying related to software product is provided which shows that the product is fit for use. In Software testing, the executions of a software component or system component are considered for the evaluation of one or more properties of interest. Generally, these properties are used to indicate the component or system in a testing process, guide its design and development. Responds are made correctly related to all kinds of inputs. In this process its all functions are performed within an acceptable duration. It is made within limited time. The components of Software testing are installed and run

in its intended environments, and provides the general result its stakeholders desire.

[2] TEST CASE MINIMIZATION

Software testing can be defined as an important and considerable step in software development. In software development, it has been noticed that the developers always depend on testing process in order to highlight and resolve the bugs. On the phase of maintenance, the size of software is enhanced as the integration of new technique is made. Addition of new technique forces that one must creates an additional test case. In regression testing, new test case is added to the test suite during the process of testing. These additions of test cases emerge the possibility of the presence of unnecessary test cases. As the limitation of time and resource, reduction techniques can be applied in order to identify and remove these redundant data.

The issue related to test suite reduction is to develop a test suite of a smaller size while retaining, if feasible and the fault detection level of the original suite. Thus it is feasible to decrease the test suite maintenance's cost. These test suit reduction techniques are also used to execute the software being tested. Therefore, it becomes feasible to reduce the overall cost of regression testing.

Regression Testing

Regression testing has been known as a special type of testing in which one tests that the changes made in a computer programs still are working with the new

changes. Regression testing is a normal part of the program development process and, in larger companies, is done by code testing specialists.

Due to these modifications, there may be any error in the execution of any system correctly. In this way, Regression Testing has become essential step in software testing. Regression Testing can be carried out with the following techniques:

Fig 1 Different Type of Regression Testing

Regression testing is performed in order to ensure that there are no side effects of new code changes on the existing functionalities. This process makes sure that the existing code in a program still works with the new changes on other part of a program. Software maintenance is an important task in which improvement; corrections of errors, optimization and make deletion of previous features are included.

Fuzzy Logic

Fuzzy logic can be understood as a form of many-valued logics. In Fuzzy Logic, the truth values related to variables can be situated between 0 and 1 both inclusive. It is analyzed that the Fuzzy Logic are used in order to deal with the concept of partial truth,

where the truth value can be completely true and completely false.

[3]LITERATURE REVIEW

A review of existing researches are stated below [P. Skrabanek et al][2018][1] proposed Models that are helpful in fuzzy linear regression. Their research work summarized fuzzy linear models that were introduced in fuzzy regression analysis. They discussed that techniques related to the test suit reduction allow business to appreciate and understand risks and issues related to the implementation software projects. Along with these feature, these test techniques are also included the process of executing a software bugs free program or application. In the process of these test suit reduction, verifying related to software product is provided which shows that the product is fit for use. The exhaustive review is extended with new models. This contribution is intended as a guide for in order to implement the different method related to fuzzy regression. Thus this research work is an inspiration for researchers..

[A. Ngah et al] [2017] [2] provided an overview of regression testing. They explained that Regression testing is very costly but also an important step in software maintenance. In this research work it has been explained that Regression testing is performed in order to ensure that there are no side effects of new code changes on the existing functionalities. This process makes sure that the existing code in a program still works with the new changes on other part of a program.

[X. Lin][2005][3] discussed Regression Testing in Research and Practice. Their observations and results have shown that although several issues are attached with research community and the industry gay but their solution is also proposed. They explained that Software maintenance is an important task in which improvement; corrections of errors, optimization and make deletion of previous features are included. Due to these modifications, there may be any error in the execution of any system correctly.

[W. E. Wong, et al][1997][4] offered the study of effective regression testing. Their proposed hybrid technique is the combination of modification, minimization and prioritization-based selection. In their research work, they used a list related to the source code changes. They also considered the

execution traces from test cases run on existing versions.

[A. Raj, et al][2017] [5] analyzed Software Testing and Defect. In their research work, the Soft Computing Concepts are also used. They explained that Regression Testing has become essential step in software testing. Regression Testing can be carried out with different techniques. They provided a comprehensive discussion on the recent trends in these fields and the application of Soft Computing concepts in the for testing and fault detection.

[M. J. Harrold et al][1990] [6] proposed a methodology to control the size of a test suite. This paper has been presented to propose a technique. Their proposed technique is able to select a representative set of test cases from a test suite. These test suites provides the same measure of coverage as the test suite. In their research work, they illustrated the methodology applying the data flow testing technique. the results and outputs of this research work indicates the effectiveness of their proposed technique.

[T. Y. Chen et al][1998][7] proposed a new heuristic for test suite reduction. In this research work, they proposed and defined a heuristic. They also defined that the issue related to test suite reduction is to develop a test suite of a smaller size while retaining, if feasible and the fault detection level of the original suite. Thus it is feasible to decrease the test suite maintenance's cost. These test suit reduction techniques are also used to execute the software being tested. Therefore, it becomes feasible to reduce the overall cost of regression testing.

[B. Vaysburg et al][2002] [8] did dependence analysis in reduction of requirement based test suites. They discussed that Requirement-based automated test case generation is a model- based technique. It has been used to generate the test suites according to individual requirements. In this research work, it has been explained that these techniques are able to significantly decrease a number of test cases.

[J. A. Jones][2003][9] discussed the test-suite decrement and prioritization for modified condition / decision coverage. In order to highlight the issues related to test-suite size, this research was made. In their research work, they used test-suite reduction algorithms to identify a decreased test suite. It was performed to achieve the same coverage related to software. In addition to this, this paper also presented

new algorithms in order to decrease the test-suite and prioritization.

[T. Y. Chen et al][2003][10] wrote on the divide-and-conquer concept. This concept was proposed for test suite reduction. During of testing of a program, the testers are required to create a set of test case. It is essential that these sets satisfy to the testing objective. The results of this research work offered a better understanding on structural properties of representative sets.

[M. P. E. Heimdahl][2004] [11] presented the discussion on test-suite reduction for model based tests. In their work, the research performed an experiment applying a large case example of a Flight Guidance System. Their results of their research work shown that there are the chance to make in specification based test-suites. In addition, they also described the experiment and outputs of their work. Along with this, the results and implications for testing are analyzed based on formal specifications.

[T. Y. Chen et al][1998][12] presented a simulation study on some heuristics for test suite reduction. Their research presented the result related to their simulation study on four heuristics. They provided an application guideline which was their objective. They did this work to choose the most suitable heuristic to be used for reduction of test suite.

[T. Xie][2004] [13] proposed the Rostra. It was an outline to make detection in redundant object-oriented unit tests. This paper was proposed to define Rostra. During the software evolution, the enhanced size of its modifications may make increment in cost of its regression integration testing. Therefore it is essential to have a mechanism to reduce the resource expenditure and testing cost. The results and outputs of their experiment have shown that Jtest and JCrasher are able to generate high percentage redundant tests. They also discussed that Rostra is efficient to eliminate these redundant tests without decreasing the quality of test suites.

[J. Black, et al][2004][14] did research on Bi-criteria models for all-uses test suite reduction. The Results of their research work indicated that test suites can be decreased regarding an assortment of program faults.

[D. Hao, et al][2005][15] did study to eliminate the harmful redundancy for testing-based fault localization. For this purpose they considered the reduction in test suite. In order to analyze the TBFL, they did an experimental study on this topic. The

results of this experiment shown that the use of TBFL may be very beneficial to fulfill this objective.

[4]PROBLEM STATEMENT

However there have been several researches in relevant field. But it has been observed that they have their own limitations. These models are unable to resolve several testing issues due to uncertainties. This uncertainty arises due to advent programming techniques and logics that are supporting artificial intelligence. Thus systems make use of neural network and fuzzy logic in order to create random behavior in programming modules. Fuzzy logic is supposed to tackle such situation thus it has been observed that there is need to integrate fuzzy logic in regression testing model to resolve issues in testing of software models.

[5]MATLAB

MATLAB is considered as a simulation tool in this exposition work. One of the technical computing languages is MATLAB. In MATLAB atmosphere matrix is called as rectangular number array. Its meaning is linked to 1x1 matrices. Numeric and non-numeric data is stored through different methods in MATLAB. This language has interactive atmosphere and is also known as high stage language. As compared to the programming languages like C, C++, COBOL, PASCAL and FORTRAN, MATLAB allows us to achieve computational mission faster. The whole thing is considered as matric in beginning. MATLAB operations are intended to be natural. MATLAB runs with complete matrices very quickly and softly while other programming language except MATLAB works only with one number at one time.[23]

Characteristics of Matlab

The most dynamic and simplest software for scientists and engineers is the MATLAB. The several features of MATLAB are as follows:

1. To perform technical computing, High level language is used.
2. To manage data, code and files it consists of development environment.
3. In case of various routing schemes and wireless sensor network MATLAB allows analysis of various parameters.
4. For linear algebra, numerical integration and statistics MATLAB consist of filtering,

Fourier analysis, optimization, mathematical functions.

5. MATLAB have been used for simulation in the research of several wireless sensor networks.
6. Data visualization has been done by various two dimensional and three dimensional graphics functions.
7. Various tools to perform automated testing with the use of automation tools like ML unit is provided by MATLAB.
8. Graphical, custom and user interfaces are built by a kit of MATLAB.
9. Many functions to integrate MATLAB algorithm is present. This also have outer application with PASCAL, C, C++, FORTRAN and PASCAL as programming language.

As it is started, MATLAB appears with its default layout.

FIG 2 Composition of Desktop

[6]CONCLUSION

As several researches in relevant field are facing issues of random behavior. These models are unable to resolve several testing problems because of such circumstances. Issues are arising as there is rapid advent of latest programming tools and logics. Such logics are applicable in artificial intelligence based application. Proposed work that is integrating fuzzy logic to regression module is supposed to tackle such situation. Proposed regression testing model is capable to resolve issues in testing of software models.

[7]FUTURE SCOPE

Research considers techniques for regression testing that would be useful for that seeker who would require knowing about this concept. This research work would be helpful because it includes regression testing and its influence. The proposed fuzzy logic based model would be beneficial to resolve the issues related to software testing. It would be used to know and decide which one performs best. This work would be helpful in future for those who want to know about Regression testing and its different techniques.

REFERENCE

- [1] P. Skrabanek and J. Marek, "Models used in fuzzy linear regression," 17th Conf. Appl. Math. APLIMAT 2018 - Proc., vol. 2018-February, no. February, pp. 955–964, 2018.
- [2] A. Ngah, M. Munro, and M. Abdallah, "An overview of regression testing," J. Electron. Comput. Eng., vol. 9, no. 3-5 Special Issue, pp. 45–49, 2017.
- [3] X. Lin, "Regression Testing in Research And Practice," 2005.
- [4] W. E. Wong, J. R. Horgan, S. London, and H. Agrawal, "Study of effective regression testing in practice," Proc. Int. Symp. Softw. Reliab. Eng. ISSRE, no. December 1997, pp. 264–274, 1997.
- [5] A. Raj, A. Upadhyay, and V. Nakhate, "Software Testing and Defect Analysis Using Soft Computing Concepts," Int. J. Sci. Technol. Res., vol. 6, no. 6, pp. 210–216, 2017.
- [6] M. J. Harrold and M. Lou Soffa, "A Methodology for Controlling the Size of A Test Suite *," 1990.
- [7] T. Y. Chen and M. F. Lau, "A new heuristic for test suite reduction'," vol. 40, pp. 347–354, 1998.
- [8] T. Y. Chen and M. F. Lau, "A simulation study on some heuristics for test suite reduction," vol. 40, pp. 777–787, 1998.
- [9] B. Vaysburg and L. H. Tahat, "Dependence Analysis in Reduction of Requirement Based Test Suites," pp. 107–111, 2002.
- [10] J. A. Jones and M. J. Harrold, "Test-Suite Reduction and Prioritization for Modified Condition / Decision Coverage."2003.
- [11] T. Y. Chen and M. F. Lau, "On the divide-and-conquer approach towards test suite reduction," vol. 152, pp. 89–119, 2003.
- [12] M. P. E. Heimdahl and D. George, "Test-Suite Reduction for Model Based Tests: Effects on Test Quality and Implications for Testing *."2004.
- [13] T. Xie, "Rostra : A Framework for Detecting Redundant Object-Oriented Unit Tests," no. Ase, pp. 196–205, 2004.
- [14] J. Black, E. Melachrinoudis, and D. Kaeli, "Bi-Criteria Models for All-Uses Test Suite Reduction," 2004.
- [15] D. Hao, L. Zhang, H. Zhong, H. Mei, and J. Sun, "Eliminating Harmful Redundancy for Testing-Based Fault Localization Using Test Suite Reduction : An Experimental Study," 2005.
- [16] S. McMaster and A. M. Memon, "Call Stack Coverage for Test Suite Reduction." 2005. Department of Computer Science, University of Maryland, College Park, MD 20742, 2005
- [17] S. Sprenkle, S. Sampath, E. Gibson, L. Pollock, and A. Souter, "An Empirical Comparison of Test Suite Reduction Techniques for User-session-based Testing of Web Applications."2005.
- [18] D. B. Jeffrey, "TEST SUITE REDUCTION WITH SELECTIVE REDUNDANCY," 2005.
- [19] G. Fraser and F. Wotawa, "Redundancy Based Test-Suite Reduction," pp. 291–305, 2007.
- [20] C. Liu, L. Chen, and C. Hsu, "An association-based case reduction technique for case-based reasoning," vol. 178, pp. 3347–3355, 2008.
- [21] S. Parsa, A. Khalilian, and Y. Fazlalizadeh, "A New Algorithm to Test Suite Reduction Based on Cluster Analysis." 2009
- [22] D. Y. Kichigin, "A Method of Test Suite Reduction for Regression Integration Testing," vol. 35, no. 5, pp. 282–290, 2009.
- [23] X. Chen, L. Zhang, and Q. Gu, "A Test Suite Reduction Approach Based on Pairwise Interaction of Requirements," pp. 1390–1397, 2011
- [24] K. Muthyala, "A NOVEL APPROACH TO TEST SUITE REDUCTION USING DATA MINING," vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 0–1, 2011.
- [25] J. Regehr, Y. Chen, P. Cuoq, and E. Eide, "Test-Case Reduction for C Compiler Bugs," pp. 335–345, 2012.
- [26] S. Xu, H. Miao, and H. Gao, "Test Suite Reduction Using Weighted Set Covering Techniques," pp. 2–7, 2012.
- [27] S. Sampath and R. C. Bryce, "Improving the effectiveness of test suite reduction for user-session-based testing of web applications," Inf. Softw. Technol., vol. 54, no. 7, pp. 724–738, 2012.
- [28] L. Vidács, Á. Beszédes, D. Tengeri, I. Siket, and T. Gyimóthy, "Test Suite Reduction for Fault

Detection and Localization : A Combined Approach,” pp. 204–213, 2014.

[29] A. Gotlieb and D. Marijan, “FLOWER : optimal test suite reduction as a network maximum flow,” no. July, 2014.

[30] A. Shi, T. Yung, A. Gyori, and D. Marinov, “Comparing and Combining Test-Suite Reduction and Regression Test Selection,” pp. 237–247, 2015.